

Utilization of Product Life Cycle Decision Making Models for Enhancing Job Effectiveness of Staff in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The paper examined utilization of product life cycle decision making model (PLCDMM) for enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent product life cycle decision making model is used for enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Four objectives, Research questions and Hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study comprises of 1559 staff in River State University and Ignatus Ajuru University of Education all in Rivers State. A cluster sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 480 respondents made up of RSU 280 and IAUE 200. Instruments for data collection were 20 items questionnaire tagged "Utilization of Product life cycle decision making model for enhancing staff job effectiveness in River State University's questionnaire" (UPLCDMMQ). The questionnaire were developed on 4-point rating scale of Very high extent (VHE-4points), High Extent (HE- 3points), Moderate Extent (ME- 2points) and Low Extent (LE-1point) and was validated by two Business Educators and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation in Faculty of Education Rivers State University Port-Harcourt. A reliability Coefficient of 0.82 was established using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool. It was determined through a pilot test carried out on 20 independent respondents outside the study area to establish the internal consistency. The administration of the instrument was done by the researchers with the help of two assistant and the instrument retrieval was on the spot. Where retrieval on the spot was not feasible, the researchers went back for collection within two weeks. Out of 480 copies administered only 461 (97%) copies was retrieved and used for analysis. Data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. Findings revealed that Product life cycle decision making model is utilized to low extent on staff recruitment and retirement while high extent on growth/development and maturity stages for enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Based on the findings, the study recommends that University administrator should adopt Product lifecycle decision making model in the recruitment of staff, establish clear objectives, and involve staff in training decision making, Provide regular workshop and seminars to enhance growth, development and staff effectiveness in job performance amongst others.

Key Words: Utilization, Product Life cycle decision making model and Staff Job effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

Business entities are social constructs created by an individual or group of individuals in a society to achieve a specific purpose through the means of planning and coordinated activity (Farham, 1999). Additionally, Robbin (1996) avers that Business entities are conscious co-coordinated social unit composed of two or more people that function on a relatively continues bases to achieve set goals. Specifically, these people are staff that was recruited to perform different but, inter-related functions for service delivery and achievement of organization goals (Amesi, 2021). Thus, the assertion indicates that organization is a service and profit oriented entities encapsulated by people with functional responsibilities to accomplish goals by means of planning and coordinated efforts. Undoubtedly, planning and coordination are managerial functions objectively driven by decision making to enhance job effectiveness in working environment especially academic institutions such as University (Porter, 2019). University is a citadel of learning where decision making is sacrosanct and directed toward character molding for life-long achievement. It encompasses learning organization with accredited departments and faculties for nurturing and fostering academic excellence. University organization is spontaneous business environment with specific functions of impetrating knowledge, moderation of characters and development of skills for self-reliant (Porter, 2019). As a citadel of learning and working environment,

University, is enclave with staff and managerial responsibilities to be accomplished through effective decision making. Thus, achieving organizational goal depends on many intervening variables including management of operation, planning and adoption of decision-making model for energizing job performance and staff effectiveness in organization (Mittal, 2016). Imperatively, Kedia & Harveston (2019) also laid credence and emphasizes on management decision making as a vital component of organizational behaviors' and a tool for enhancing academic staff effectiveness in job performance particularly in fast-paced University environment.

Staff effectiveness is very crucial and entails regularity, healthiness, efficiency, internalization, instructional delivery and coordination of academic and non-academic programme for development of university (Dziuban, Moskal & Williams, 2021). Staff effectiveness also denotes ability to influencing students' academic outcome, research productivity and institutional reputation (Gupta & Starr, 2022). This could be achieved through intrinsic and extrinsic motivational which is direct relationship with transformational leadership that provides direction and decision making on professional development of staff, work-life balancing, recognitions and enhancing job satisfaction amongst others. However, enhancing staff effectiveness in University job performances is encompassing (Mittal, 2016). It involves broad based

managerial functions enclaved in planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting and budgeting geared towards enhancing staff effectiveness and job performance for achievement of set goals. The aforementioned managerial functions cannot be attained without effective decision making (Amesi, 2021).

Decision making is the process of chain of events involving identifying, analyzing and choosing the best alternative for a cause of action and implementation. Decision making is a vital managerial tool that enables organization to respond to changing business trend and market condition, capitalizing on novel skills and methodology under advancing technology (Gupta & Starr, 2022). Thus, it is beneficial for university administration to constantly engage in reliable and effective decision making for organization's success (Kedia & Harveston, 2019). Different decision-making models abound but, enterprises and University organizations need an in-depth study of their heterogeneous activities to align with the most effective models like Product life cycle decision making to suit their business endeavor.

According to Gupta and Starr (2019), Product life cycle decision making model is a systematic decision-making approach that provides a framework for managing staff lifespan and job effectiveness in University. It also takes into consideration of decision making analogy from staff recruitment through growth, development and to retirement. Product life cycle decision making model had been proving to be effective with driving managerial principle and standard that gained significant attention in product manufacturing industries globally. In recent time however, the model has attracted the attention of researchers who deeply emphasize on its importance and usage in various organizational contexts mostly in university institution for enhancing staff effectiveness and efficiency in job performances. Therefore, this paper examined the utilization of product life cycle decision making models for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff in Rivers State Universities.

Decision Making for Staff and Organizational Effectiveness

Outlining the characteristics and principle of organizational behavior, Amesi, (2021) averred that decision making is the process of selecting a course of action from available options to achieve a desired outcome or solve individual and organizational problems. It involves identification, selection, evaluation, consideration and choosing of the best alternatives based on criteria of feasibility, risk and potentials consequences. As a process, decision making, involves chronological stages starting from problem

identification to implementations and determination of outcome (Akpomi, 2020). Additionally, decision making is however, only a step in planning staff effectiveness and organization productivity. Managers sometime see decision making as their central job because they must constantly choose what is to be done, who is to do it, when, where and how it will be done (Gupta & Starr, 2022). Thus, decision making is vital in organization life span. It enhances job effectiveness, increases productivity, facilitates communication, environmental friendliness and provides dynamic principles for attainment of set goals. Thus, any wrong decision made adversely affects staff effectiveness and organization productivity. Decision making involves several models including rational decision making, bounded rationality; garbage can amongst others and use of any depends on the nature of problem, the organizational context and cognitive scope of the manager (Katz & Kahn, 1965). However, in university job effectiveness and performance where tangible and intangible products are produced, Product Life cycle decision making model is sacrosanct to be used.

Product Life Cycle Decision Making Model for Staff Effectiveness

Product lifecycle decision making model is a systematic approach in decision making for achieving organizational job effectiveness goals (Kedia & Harveston, 2019). The model offers an organization an in-depth knowledge and opportunity for making informed decision that enhances productivity and staff effectiveness. The model was propounded by Raymond Vernon in 1960. Vernon avers that Product life cycle model is a critical model that considers product life span and transcends to longevity of time that organization's product and her workers exist for business productivity. Thus, in university productivity Product life decision making considers the time staff were recruited and its effectiveness in job performances and productive competitiveness. Thus, the time for recruitment and time for retirement are crucial stages for job performance. Product lifecycle decision making has four stages which include Introduction stage, growth, maturity and declining stage in product manufacturing organization. These stages are equally translated to recruitment stage, development and training, internalization/sustenance and retirement stages in service organization like University. The importance of these stages is pertinent and cannot be overemphasized in organizational management. (Gupta & Starr, 2022).

Recruitment Stage of Product Life Cycle Decision Making and Staff Effectiveness

Every organization in a competitive business environment considers management and decision

making as a veritable tool to achieving success (Kumar & Singh, 2017). Thus, Product lifecycle decision making model provide a framework for managing staff from recruitment to retirement stage. Therecruitment stage takes into consideration the organization productivity and the staff demographic variables such as age, sex, qualifications, experiences, cultural background, work abilities, Perception and other psycho-social dimension relating to job effectiveness and productivity performances. The essence is to employ a suitable staff that stands the taste of time and compete with others to achieving organization success (Kumar & Singh, 2017). In public services, Product Life cycle decision making model provides the administrators with tactical knowledge to recruit experience and energized staff at initial stages. It considers different analytical planning and decision making base on applicants' demographic variables. The planning stage takes into consideration the applicants' strength and weakness and organization's opportunities and technologies in use for job performance and productivity. Thus, recruitment stage focuses on identifying the organization needs, defining objectives and developing strategies for recruiting staff to ensure effectiveness and efficiency in job performance (Kumar & Singh, 2017). In universities, life cycle decision recruitment stage considers life span of the staff which terminates at age of 65 to 70 as the case may be. This signifies that age and experience are determinant factors in university staff recruitment and effectiveness. In support Collins (2019) observed that, Product life cycle decision making initiate plans and approach in a sequential order to enhance growth and development of the staff for goal achievement before retirement to enhance job effectiveness. Pertinently, recruitment stage of Product life cycle decision model on staff is very essential for growth of university as any mistake made at the initial stage may devastate the growth and wellbeing of the staff and entire university.

Growth and Development Stage of Product Life Cycle Decision Making Model for Enhancing Staff Effectiveness

The growth and development stage of Product life cycle decision making model is a critical phase characterized by rapid expansion and development of ideas for high productivity, awareness, promotion of the business, workers effectiveness, spontaneous customers' retention, business profit, maintenance of business goodwill and proficiency of staff (Dziuban & William 2021). At this stage effective decision making is required to develop staff creative thinking and innovative skills for sustenance of organization competitiveness, staff effectiveness and spontaneous

turnover (Akpomi, 2020). Growth stages of life decision making model involves different dimension including marketing expansion, development and introduction of new product and services that attracts patronage from customers, building infrastructural base and capabilities to ensuring human resources management by recruiting and developing skills and talents in staff which undoubtedly are pivotal elements in a progressive business (Porter, 2019). Universities staff at this stage need to be guided with a procedural decision making to enhance their rationality on the job growth, development and sustenance. Thus, Product life cycle decision making at this stage leverages on staff technical skills, communication skills and interpersonal skills amongst others to advance competencies required for new programme development and expansion that mitigate global changes in educational trends. However, managing staff effectiveness in growth and development stage of product life cycle decision model is very critical and anchored on the strategies adopted for training, mental health development, motivational strategy and commitment for general wellbeing of staff to activate knowledge on job performance (Dziuban & William 2021). In addition, Dziuban and William avers that management of workers at the growth stage is very critical; it increases revenue for expansion of market share and introduction of new product and services. It improves competitiveness by developing capabilities and infrastructural facilities to the organization. Furthermore, it enhances good reputation and goodwill by building brand recognition and credibility in staff recruitment (Kedia & Harveston, 2019).

Maturity Stage of Product Life Cycle Decision Model for Staff Effectiveness

Maturity stage of Product life cycle decision making model is very critical stage in the retention of staff and sustenance university development. It is a stage where staff is on its high peak on job performance and Product life cycle decision model may be used to deepen functionalities and staff effectiveness for optimizing productivity. Furthermore, maturity stage of life cycle decision model is the most profitable stage where business productivity is receiving high patronage within and outside immediate environment (Opatha, 2015). At this stage, cost of implementation is highly operational and staff abides by rules for services delivery. It is also a stage that organization is saturated with different decision outcome and competition among the emerging enterprises hence, benefit of the decision may start to diminish and clamoring for changes for survival at long-run equilibrium (Porter, 2019). The stage is predominated by consolidation and strengthening existing processes of system upgrade, renewal or innovation of

ideals, policy line for adapting to changing market condition. At this stage product life cycle decision making is also necessary for effective management and assessment of staff job performances and making adjustment to face emerging competitors (Akpomi, 2020). Ajerinde (2020), affirmed that the essence of effective workers management during maturity stage is to enhance efficiency and streamline on the process that reduces cost of control. Matti (2022) clearly observed that, maturity stage of product life decision making model improves staff effectiveness and job performances, ensures increased quality of productivity as well as boosting staff moral for job satisfaction and engagement. Despite its relevancy, maturity stage of staff in any organization faces crucial challenges of compliance and resistance to changes in innovation, increased market pressure and declining motivation for increased competition on the aging workforce. Thus, at this stage, Product life cycle decision making model could be used to guide managers on strategies to be adopted for effective management and enhancement of workers as well take a decisive action to uphold principles and conduct of the business to consolidate on the achievement of the organization. Furthermore, to overcome the challenges managers ought to foster for innovation to encourage creativity among the working force, develop a good leadership style, foster for good communication channel to enhance good relationship and quality feedback to staff and emphasize on training which support and boost staff learning and effectiveness in organization (Opatha, 2015).

Retirement Stage of Product Life Cycle Decision Making Model for Enhancement of Staff Effectiveness

Retirement or declining stage is the final phase of life cycle decision making model in an organization. It is a critical stage in organization life which produces physical goods or intangible product in a competitive environment. Retirement stage to staff life is characterized by decreased in job performance, reduction in the market index and diminishing resources that incapacitate organization's productivity and future existence (Adeized, 2017). In addition, Collins (2019) averred that during retirement stage, staff productivity shrinks, sale volume and revenue drastically dropped to the barest minimum, high decrease in profitability, loss of key personnel, loss of creativity and innovative strategy including low operational standard are largely paramount to jeopardize business wellbeing. Kotter (2017) stated that retirement stage is a natural phenomenon caused by age factor, business trends, increased competition, lack of innovation, economic downturn and myopic resistance to adopt globalization

amongst others. Causes of staff retirement are enormous and devastating however, the adoption of Product life cycle decision making model bridges the gap in staff effectiveness and job performance. Thus, Gupta & Starr (2022) opined that at staff retirement stage, management should re-strategized and effectively utilize Product life cycle decision making model strategies such as constant research and development training, reduction in work load and increase in staff motivation to mitigate devastating effects of retirement.

Product Life Cycle Decision Making Model Utilization in Nigerian Universities

Generally, staff in Nigerian Universities is the most difficult asserts to manage in terms of job effectiveness and performance (Adizes, 2017). Thus, utilization of product life cycle decision model is vital for high productivity and success of university staff. The utilization of Product life cycle decision making model and its benefits stem from four different areas of recruitment, training and development, performance management and staff retention in retirement stages. In recruitment stage, Product life cycle decision making is essentially required for selection of competent staff to fill available position in University. The essence is to ensure efficient and longevity of staff and University life (Dziuban et al, 2021). In the process of recruitment, strategic planning is used to define job requirement and description, evaluate the candidate ability to cope with the requirements for job effectiveness and performance. Training and Development of PLCDDMM is essential for staff proficiency. This is done during growth stage where evaluation and assessment of effectiveness of employee is significantly necessary. Training and development of University staff enhances effective job performances and staff reliability in the face of competition and challenges (Akpomi, 202). In Product life cycle decision model, the adoption of analytical strategy is applied to identify performance gap and implementation challenges in growth stage. The reason for identification is to develop improvement plans for overall University development and staff job performance (Kedia & Harveston, 2019). At maturity and retirement stage of University staff there is always a high rate of staff turnover. Hence, Product life cycle decision making model is utilized in planning staff retention strategy, in development, maturity and retirement stages to enhance job satisfaction. The essence is to develop a refined approach to enhance effectiveness and job performance and staff retention for high productivity (Porter, 2019). Furthermore, retention plan strategy engenders inter and intra communication that enhance staff suitability and benefits to University community. Still on relevancy

and benefits of Product life cycle decision making model Collins (2019) averred that it improves job efficiency and productivity, increased staff job satisfaction and enhance staff growth. Furthermore, most decision making model are deficient in hierarchical management and motivation but, the utilization of product lifecycle decision making model encourage administrative hierarchy and ensures effective motivation of staff in different stages of job performance and promotes cooperation among University staff (Comeron & Quinn, 2017).

However, every decision making model has its peculiar challenges in University management. Therefore, Product life cycle decision making model suffer challenges. staff may abide to the principle at recruitment level but may inadvertently dislike and resist it during growth and maturity stages (Milla, 2016). This is because staff inherently dislike work and may intentionally resist change especially the policies that affect their growth and development. In addition, Kedia & Harveston (2019) averred that limitations and insufficient resources may hinder effective utilization of Product life cycle decision model and jeopardizes management of staff in University organizations. In spite of the challenges however, it is obvious, that product life cycle decision making model is crucial for staff growth and survival in today's fast-paced University environment. Pertinently, Universities are ill-informed about Product life cycle decision making model. Thus, its utilization becomes obscure to university administrators and affecting staff effectiveness and job performance. To this end, the researchers deemed it fit to investigate the utilization of life cycle decision making model for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff in Rivers State University

Statement of Problem

University staff in Nigerian is among public service sectors that faces challenges on different stages of job effectiveness and performance. This may be as result of oversight and job proximity which decision plans for staff recruitment, growth, development and retirement were not effectively optimized to enhance job effectiveness of academic staff due to many factors including ill-utilization of proper decision making models which impact greatly on teaching quality, research development and overall job effectiveness and performances of staff in Rivers State University. In spite of the critical roles and efforts of Director of Academic Planning (DAP) in providing workshops, seminar and training to enhance staff productivity, growth and development, there is still significant gap in job effectiveness and performance of staff. The gaps are

obviously manifesting in low productivity which stakeholders attributed to inadequate planning on staff career stages, insufficient alignment of staff development programme and limited consideration of staff motivational factors on each segment of work life which is specifically anchored on Product life cycle decision making model. Product life cycle decision making model offers a systematic approach to enhancing staff effectiveness in job performances, fosters for improved productivity, increase job satisfaction, and reduction in staff turnover. However, it has been observed that many universities in Nigeria are ill-informed about Product life cycle decision making model and its utilization for staff effectiveness in job performance. Thus, staff is encumbered with high work load resulting to ineffectiveness in job performance from recruitment through growth and maturity stages and suffers at retirement stage without visible decision plan in work life. These remarkable notices was worrisome and attracted the attention of the researchers to investigate the utilization of life cycle decision making model for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate utilization of life cycle decision making models for enhancing job effectiveness staff in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
2. Determine the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model on staff growth and development stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
3. Determine the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities
4. Determine the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?
2. To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

3. To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?
4. To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilizes product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilizes product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities
4. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilizes product life cycle decision making models in staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Response of RSU and IAUE on the Extent Administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Extent utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities	IAUE (Number 195)			RSU (Number 266)		
		M	SD	RM K	M	SD	RM K
1	Utilizing recruitment decision based on age of applicant for enhancing staff job effectiveness.	2.63	0.84	HE	2.73	0.29	HE
2	Utilizing decision based on past and cognitive experiences for enhancing staff job effectiveness	2.16	1.01	LE	2.04	1.04	LE
3	Utilizing decision based on area of specialization for enhancing staff job effectiveness	2.67	0.75	HE	2.56	0.11	HE
4	Utilizing decision based on ensuring best candidates are employed for enhancing staff job effectiveness	2.07	0.62	HE	2.20	1.01	LE

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 1,599 respondents made academic staff members in RSU 1017 and IAUE students 582. The study adopted cluster sampling technique to select 280 from RSU and 200 from IAUE making total of 480 respondents. Instruments for data collection were 20 items questionnaire tagged “Utilization of Product life cycle decision making model for enhancing staff job effectiveness in River State University’s questionnaire” (ULCDMMQ). The questionnaire was developed on 4-point rating scale of Very high extent (VHE-4 points), High Extent (HE- 3 points), Moderate Extent (ME- 2points) and Low Extent (LE-1point) and was validated by two Business educators and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation all in Faculty of Education Rivers State University Port-Harcourt. A reliability Coefficient of 0.82 was established using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool for the study. It was determined through a pilot test carried out on 20 independent respondents outside the study area to establish the internal consistency. The administration of the instrument was done by the researchers with the help of two assistant and retrieval of the instrument was on the spot. Out of 480 copies of instrument administered only 461 copies was retrieved representing 97% retrieval. Data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The decision rule for acceptance was any mean higher than 2.50 is considered to be high extent while mean below 2.50 is considered low extent

5	Utilizing decision based on mental and physical fitness to enhancing staff job effectiveness	2.43	0.71	HE	2.48	1.03	LE
G/mean & SD		2.39	0.79		2.40	0.70	

Source: Field Study, 2024

Table 1 above revealed the extent Administrators utilize product life cycle decision making models in recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff in Rivers State Universities. Item 1 and 3 has mean scores of 2.63 and 2.67 for IAUE while 2.73 and 2.56 for RSU which is slightly above 2.50 criterions graded as high extent. While item 2,4 and 5 has mean score of 2.16, 2.07 and 2.43 and 2.04, 2.20 and 2.48 for IAUE and RSU which was below 2.50 criterions graded under low extent. However, the grand mean of 2.39 and 2.40 for IAUE and RUS respectively indicated that

University administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models in recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness of staff to low extent in Rivers State Universities

Research Question 2: To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Response of IAUE and RSU staff on the Extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development for enhancing job effectiveness	IAUE (Number 195)			RSU (Number 266)		
		X	SD	RM K	X	SD	RM K
6	Utilizing retunes training decision for skill development and efficiency for enhancing staff job effectiveness	3.08	0.81	HE	3.04	0.90	HE
7	Utilizing decision on giving research grants to enhance staff job effectiveness	3.2	0.78	HE	2.91	0.98	HE
8	Decision for on the job seminar and workshop for enhancing staff job effectiveness	3.12	0.96	HE	3.03	0.92	HE
9	Decision to encouraging further study and development for enhancing job effectiveness	2.97	0.84	HE	3.05	0.96	HE
10	Decision for promoting only principal officers enhances staff job effectiveness	2.48	1.09	LE	2.33	1.09	LE
G/ mean & SD		2.97	0.90		2.87	0.97	

Source: Field Study 2024

Table 2 above shows the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on growth and development stages of staff for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. The table revealed that item 1, 2, 3, and 4 has mean scores of 3.08, 3.2, 3.12 and 2.97 for IAUE while 3.04, 2.91, 3.03, and 3.05 for RSU which is above 2.50 criterions graded as high extent. Item 2 have a mean score of 2.48 and 1.87 for IAUE and RSU below 2.50 criterions graded under low extent. The grand mean of 2.97 and

2.87 for IAUE and RSU respectively indicated that administrators utilize life cycle decision making models on growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff to high extent in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 3: To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Response of IAUE and RSU staff extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness of in Rivers State Universities	IAUE (Number 195)			RSU (Number 266)		
		X	SD	RM K	X	SD	RM K
11	Utilizing regular promotion decision on maturity stage for enhancing job effectiveness	2.85	1.00	HE	2.90	1.00	HE
12	Utilizing fringe benefit decision enhances staff job effectiveness	3.08	1.00	HE	3.14	0.88	HE
13	Utilizingsalary increment and recognition decisions for enhancing staff job effectiveness	3.14	0.84	HE	3.07	0.87	HE
14	Utilizing high work load decisionon maturity/sustenance stage for enhancing staff job effectiveness	2.21	1.04	LE	2.27	1.06	LE
15	Utilizing appointment decision into sensitive position for enhancing staff job effectiveness	3.16	0.83	HE	2.93	0.93	HE
G/mean& SD		2.89	0.94		2.86	0.75	

Source: Field Study 2024

Table 3 above revealed the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model on maturity and sustenance stage of work for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. Item 16, 17, 18 and 20 have mean scores of 2.85, 3.08, 3.14, and 3.16 for IAUE while 2.90, 3.14, 3.07 and 2.93 for RSU which is above 2.50 criterions graded as high extent. While item 19 has mean score of 2.21 and 2.27 for IAUE and RSU are below 2.50 criterions graded under low extent. However, the grand mean of 2.89 and

2.86 for IAUE and RSU respectively indicated that administrators utilize life cycle decision making model to high extent on maturity and sustenance stage of work for enhancing job effectiveness of academic staff in Rivers State.

Research Question 4: To what extent do administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Response of IAUE and RSU staff extent administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on retirement stages for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities	IAUE (Number 195)			RSU (Number 266)		
		X	SD	RM K	X	SD	RM K
16	Utilizing reduction of work load decision for enhancing staff job effectiveness on retirement stage	2.11	1.13	LE	2.26	1.09	LE
17	Regular approval decision on staff sabbatical leave for enhancing job effectiveness	2.24	1.08	LE	2.19	1.10	LE
18	Retention of staff for contract decision after retirement enhances job effectiveness	2.16	1.07	LE	2.02	1.00	LE
19	Utilizing decision plans to retiring indolent staff at un-estimated time enhances job effectiveness	2.72	0.91	HE	2.83	0.92	HE
20	Utilizing Decision to pay allowances and gratuity prompt enhances staff job effectiveness	3.08	0.96	HE	3.10	0.90	HE
G/mean& SD		2.46	1.03		2.48	1.00	

Source: Field Study 2024

Table 4 above revealed the extent University administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making model on staff Retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Item 16, 17, 18 have mean scores of 2.11, 2.24, 2.16, for IAUE while 2.26, 2.19 and 2.02, for RSU which is below 2.50 criterions graded as low extent. While item 19 and 20 has mean score of 2.72 and 3.08 for IAUE, 2.83 and 3.10

for RSU which are above 2.50 criterions graded high extent. However, the grand mean of 2.46 and 2.48 for IAUE and RSU respectively indicated that administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model to extent on staff Retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent

administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Table 5: A Summary of t-test analysis of RSU and IAUE on the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Response	N	X	SD	Df	Alp	t.cal	t-crit	Decision
IAUE	195	2.39	0.79	459	0.05	0.004	1.96	Retained
RSU	266	2.40	0.70					

Source: Field study 2024

The table 5 above revealed the responses on the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making models in staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. Data in the table shows that the t-cal. of 0.004 with degree of freedom of 459 at 0. 05 levels of significant is less than the t-crit. of 1.96. Therefore, the hypothesis is retained. This means that the responses of RSU staff do not significantly differ with IAUE staffon the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision

making models in staff recruitment stage for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities

Hypothesis: 2. There is no significant difference in mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Table 6: A Summary of t-test analysis of RSU and IAUE staff responses on the extent Administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Response	N	X	SD	Df.	Alp.	t.cal.	t-crit.	Decision
IAUE	195	2.97	0,90	459	0.05	1.11	1.96	Retained
RSU	266	2.87	0,97					

Source: Field Study, 2024

The table 6 above revealed the responses of IAUE and RSU Staff responses on the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. Data in the table shows that the t-cal. of 1.11 with degree of freedom of 459 at 0. 05 levels of significant is less than the t-crit. of 1.96. Therefore the hypothesis is retained. This means that the responses RSU staff do not significantly differs with IAUE staff on the extent

administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Hypothesis:3. There is no significant difference in mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Table 7: A Summary of t-test analysis of RSU and IAUE staff responses on the extent Administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff maturity and sustenance stages for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities

Response	N	X	SD	Df.	Alp	t. cal.	t-crit.	Decision
IAUE	195	2.89	0.94	459	0.05	0.38	1.96	Retained
RSU	266	2.86	0.76					

Source: Researcher Data 2024

The table 7 above revealed the responses of Staff on the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff maturity and sustenance stages for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. Data in the table shows that the t-cal. of 0.38 with degree of freedom of 459 at 0. 05 levels of significant is less than the t-crit. of 1.96. Therefore the

hypothesis is retained. The result indicates that the responses of RSU and IAUE staff do not defer significantly on the extent administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff maturity and sustenance stages for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities

Hypothesis: 4. There is no significant difference in mean responses of RSU and IAUE staff on the extent administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision

making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Table 8: A Summary of t-test analysis of IAUE and RSU staff responses on the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

Response	N	X	SD	Df.	Alp	t. cal.	t-crit.	Decision
IAUE	195	2.46	1.03	459	0.05	0.22	1.96	Retained
RSU	266	2.48	1.00					

Source: Researcher Data 2024

The table 8 above revealed the responses of Staff on the extent administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. Data in the table shows that the t-cal. of 0.22 with degree of freedom of 459 at 0. 05 levels of significant is less than the t-crit. of 1.96. Therefore, the hypothesis is retained. The result indicates that the responses of RSU staff do not defer significantly with IAUS staff on the extent administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion of Findings

Extent of Utilization of Product Life Cycle Decision Making Models in Staff Recruitment Stage for Enhancing Job Effectiveness

The findings in utilization of product life cycle decision Making Models in Recruitment Stage as posed in research question one indicates that administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models in staff recruitment stage for enhancing Job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities to low extent. The ground mean of 2.39 for IAUE and 2.40 for RSU in analysis Table 4.1 revealed that staff agreed that University administrators utilizes Product life cycle decision making models in recruitment stage to low extent for enhancing Job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. It is only used in determining age bracket of applicants and areas of specialization while job cognitive experiences, physical fitness and others which enhance job effectiveness and performance are less considered in staff recruitment. The findings agreed with Matti (2022) that age, work experiences and physical fitness have higher effects on staff job performance in organization.

Extent of Utilization of Product Life Cycle Decision Making Models on Staff Growth and Development Stages for Enhancing Job Effectiveness

Staff growth and development stages are crucial in University organization. Thus, Product life cycle

decision making models offers positive thinking and behavioral tendencies for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities. Results in table two as posted in research question two indicates that university administrators utilize product life cycle decision making models on staff growth and development stages to high extent for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The ground mean of 2.65 and 2.97 for IAUE and RSU staff respectively indicates that Product life cycle decision making models are used to enhance job effectiveness of staff to high extent. The study found that it is utilized in staff retune training for skill development, giving grant for knowledge development, seminar and workshops that enhances work efficiency and engenders staff effectiveness and job performance for high productivity. Workshop training helps staff to upgrade in job, encouraging education for high qualification all for enhancing staff job effectiveness.

Extent Administrators Utilizes Product Life Cycle Decision Making Model on Staff Maturity and Sustenance Stage for Enhancing Job Effectiveness

The study findings in research question three indicates that university administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making model on staff maturity and sustenance stage for enhancing job effectiveness of staff in Rivers State Universities to high extent. The ground mean of 2.89 for IAUE and 2. 86 for RSU in analysis Table 4.3 revealed that RSU and IAUE staff agreed that administrators’ uses regular promotion of staff, increase in fringe benefits, staff appointment into sensitive positions amongst others to enhance staff job effectiveness at maturity and sustenance stage in Product life cycle decision making model. The utilization helps staff to gain job satisfaction, increases management performance and makes staff to be productive. The result also indicates that regular use of Product life cycle model helps staff to mitigate personal and organizational challenges for internal and external competitiveness. The result was in agreement with Porter, 2019 who observed that Product life cycle

decision making model on maturity stage enhances staff with competencies for job performance and satisfaction.

Extent Administrators Utilize Product Life Cycle Decision Making Models on Staff Retirement Stage for Enhancing Job Effectiveness.

The Findings in the study shows that staff retirement stage is inevitable. Results in table 4.4 as posted in research question four indicates that University administrators utilize Product life cycle decision making models to low extent on staff retirement stage for enhancing job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The ground mean of 2.46 for IAUE and 2.48 for RSU in analysis Table 4 revealed that staff agreed that university administrators utilize Product life cycle decision models only to retiring indolent staff and delaying allowances and gratuity to retiring staff. While increasing work load, not approving staff sabbatical leave, retiring staff and use product life cycle decision model in deciding payment pattern of all allowances and gratuity at retirement stage. The study also shows that the use of Product life cycle model at retirement stage do not encourage staff job performance and managerial effectiveness. The findings agreed with Adizes (2017) who averse that product life decision making models at declining stage effects workers experiences have higher effects on managerial performance that affects organization's productivity.

In addition, the study findings revealed in Hypotheses table 4.5, 4.6, 4.7 and 4.8 that, there was no significant difference in the mean responses of IAUE and RSU staff on the extent administrators utilize product life cycle decision making model on staff recruitment, growth and development, maturity and retirement stages for enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities

CONCLUSION

Product life cycle decision making model is significantly utilized in many organizations to enhance staff effectiveness in job performances. However, the adoption in public services and humanitarian organizations like universities is for effective decision making and administration of staff from recruitment to retirement age. Product life cycle decision making model provides a frame work for moderation of staff actions, motivates work attitude, provide a conducive working atmosphere and a procedural decision making for enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities. The result showed that product life cycle decision making model is utilized to low extent for enhancing staff job effectiveness on staff recruitment

and retirement but utilized to high extent on staff growth and development stage and maturity stages in Rivers State Universities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. Administrator in various universities should as matters of urgency adopt product lifecycle decision making model in the recruitment and retirement stages of staff to enhancing staff job effectiveness in Rivers State Universities.
2. University authorities should establish clear objectives, involve stakeholders and staff in decision making on training workshop and seminars for sustenance of staff growth and development that enhances effectiveness in job performance
3. Product life decision making models should be used to expound staff skills and experiences in maturity stage to encourage acquisition of more useful organizational skills through approval of sabbatical leave and professional degree and be more useful to university community.
4. Unit heads in Rivers State Universities should provide training and seminars to guild their retiring staff on how best to mitigate life after retirement

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